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ПРОДУКТОВ И АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННЫХ СИСТЕМ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7458373>**АННОТАЦИЯ**

В данной статье освещены общие вопросы цифровизации нефтегазового производства - применение современных программных комплексов и автоматизированных систем проектирования в нефтегазовой отрасли промышленности, применяемых в образовании. Представлены общая характеристика информационно-коммуникационных технологий, определения, приведены примеры программных комплексов, собраны обзорные данные, технические особенности различных программных продуктов, используемых в настоящее время.

Ключевые слова: программный комплекс, информационно-коммуникационные технологий, автоматизированные системы проектирования, моделирование, средства визуализации.

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technologies, PhD student**OVERVIEW OF MODERN APPLICATION SOFTWARE PRODUCTS AND
AUTOMATED SYSTEMS OIL AND GAS FACILITIES INDUSTRY FOR EDUCATION****ANNOTATION**

This article highlights the general issues of digitalization of oil and gas production - the use of modern software systems and automated design systems in the oil and gas industry in education. General characteristics are presented information and communication technologies,

definitions, examples of software systems are given, overview data are collected, technical features of various software products, currently used.

Keywords: software complex, information and communication technologies, computer-aided design systems, modeling, visualization tools.

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada neft va gaz qazib olishni raqamlashtirishning umumiy masalalari - ta'limda qo'llaniladigan neft va gaz sanoatida zamonaviy dasturiy tizimlar va avtomatlashtirilgan loyihalash tizimlaridan foydalanish yoritilgan. Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining umumiy xususiyatlari, ta'riflar keltirilgan, dasturiy majmualarga misollar keltirilgan, umumiy ma'lumotlar to'plangan, hozirgi kunda qo'llanilayotgan turli dasturiy mahsulotlarning texnik xususiyatlari.

Kalit so'zlar: dasturlar paket, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, avtomatlashtirilgan loyihalash tizimlari, modellashtirish, vizuallashtirish vositalari.

The rapid development of scientific and technical laboratories has led to a change in several stages in the development of science and technology in the modern period. Today, the development of digital and information technologies has practically brought humanity to the stage of transition to a post-industrial society, where the bulk of human potential is concentrated in the field of information management, and a smaller part is employed in the field of industrial and industrial labor (manual and mechanical laboratory).

The use of virtualization technology in education (or in school conditions) is still a relatively unexplored area. Despite the few literary sources partially dealing with this issue, we are not aware of the existence of an overview study striving to systematize possibilities and ways to employ this progressive technology within the framework of the process of education. Upon an analysis of the existing available information sources, it is possible to identify two main thought streams in respect of the employment of virtualization technology.

In the field of mechanical engineering, telecommunications and instrumentation, these processes are expressed in the form of a transition to more and more autonomous and software-controlled technical devices. At the same time, there is a unification of points of entry and control for various types of equipment, namely, the formation of a single digital-software platform is taking place, which, according to common schemes and protocols, can interact with completely different equipment. Such a platform is modern computer microprocessor technology, built on the basis of the achievements of integral technology and software, in which the development and trends of unification based on basic levels are also observed.

In the field of fundamental and applied research, there is also an increase in the complexity of the methods and principles of studying more and more "subtle" and complex technologies. For a long time, many physical structures and processes have not been observed even with an armed eye. There is also a widespread introduction of information and computing systems, with the help of which it is possible to simulate a visual model of behavior according to the studied mathematical algorithm of the process. Further, starting from software simulation, the modern approach to information systems allows you to go further and begin further research on the basis of the software model. This

significantly reduces time, financial and human resources compared to conducting research on real physical structures[1:125-126].

Interaction with installations, stands and others equipment for experiments allows you to study the subject from a practical point of view and contributes to the development of tactile memory, the development of the necessary skills and skills. However, it is not always possible to perform these works for several reasons:

- lack of the necessary instruments, equipment;
- performing work is associated with a high risk to health or life students, which is unacceptable within the educational institution;
- high cost of laboratory work due to the high cost equipment, reagents, materials;
- training is carried out remotely or in a mixed manner, which entails restricting access to laboratory facilities.

These problems can be resolved by switching to use. Virtual reality for organizing practical or laboratory classes.

Due to the high demand in the current environment (remote education, restrictions on attendance, quarantine measures, etc.) educational information systems are gaining more and more popularity and technologies, which also include virtual laboratory facilities.

Most often they are presented in the form of Internet resources or a separate application. One of the approaches to creating virtual laboratories is to use a specific platform that allows you to place three-dimensional models equipment or installations, reference material, sound and animate processes occurring in the real world. An example of such a platform is vAcademia [4:3]. However, such environments, although they allow you to quickly form educational material and distribute it to students, not always provide the best rendering quality, functionality and interactivity. An example of an application is a virtual laboratory, developed in Delphi XE and NET Framework 4.0, which consists of three parts for different laboratory works: description, theory, practice. In the practice section, using interaction with two-dimensional graphic objects, you can emulate work real equipment and write the measured data into the table. Disadvantage of this approach is the use of not the most modern and common development environments, which affects the visual component of the application.

Figure 1. P3DB / Navigator software package interface.

Virtual simulators of this kind are actively used in the case when not requires three-dimensional visualization of objects or processes, which is especially important for various consoles or flat stands.

To integrate 3D models created in various systems of automated design, and their visualization using the information system P3DB / Navigator [5:2]. This software package is convenient for interactive project tracking and viewing 3D models of industrial technological objects in the process of design, installation and operation. Enough easy-to-use interface of the program allows you to work with many CAD products with minimal knowledge of the interface of other modeling complexes. P 3DB / Navigator has the ability to merge object information from different sources and other computer-aided design systems in one model, which, in turn, helps to provide customers with only the necessary graphic part in requested format (figure 1)[2:52-53].

STAR-CCM + software package. One of the modern software products used in design objects of hydrocarbon transport systems in oil and gas industry is STARCCM + - a software package of the last generation, which can carry out the calculation of diverse problems of mechanics of continuous environments, such as: fluid dynamics, calculation reacting flows, thermodynamics, calculation mechanical load. The STARCCM + complex allows you to carry out all stages of the problem modeling in one integrated software environment [3:37-40]. This unique approach features ease of use and automated CAD (Computer Aided Design) and CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics) - models, meshes, which allows designers to achieve better results faster and better. The latest version of STAR-CCM + implements the following features: powerful new meshing tools; wide range of physical models; the use of arbitrary polyhedral cells; powerful visualization tools; reliable results; compatibility of models with existing software systems: STAR-CD, FLOWVISION, GridGen [6]. CFD modeling can be used both to address issues related to flow hydrodynamics and to create models of chemical reactions and thermodynamic effects, and carried out in the flow. The main advantages of this scientific search method are obtaining a visual representation of the nature of the ongoing processes in the object under study and study of its various designs without creating costly experimental installations. As well as optimization principles functioning in order to obtain the specified parameters of the devices.

Based on the review of software systems, it can be concluded that the use of software systems is one of important aspects in existing industries industry. Application of modern information technology allows to ensure the high quality of the calculated results, simplify the design process, reduce the influence of the human factor at the operation stage, improve technical and economic indicators in general.

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